

THE IMAGE OF WISDOM IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LITERATURE

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Abstract: *This article deals with the image of wisdom in English and Uzbek literature, as well as, folklore and the work done in this field. The information about the commonality of the wisdom image and principles of the historical similarities of English and Uzbek folklore is given. Folklore samples that poetically reflect the national ideology and psyche of the people are noteworthy for their deep ideology and art. The centuries' old dreams, aspirations, struggle for freedom and liberty of the ancestors, the pain and suffering on this path, the characters, the unique traditions are seen as important features of the national mentality.*

Key words: *folklore, poetry, character, tradition, genre, epos, Alpomish, Beowulf*

Oral word art is expressed with “folklore” or “Folk oral poetic creation” terms. The term folklore was first used by the 19th century explorer William Thomas in 1846. It consists of two words- “folk” people, “lore”- knowledge, wisdom. Therefore, folklore is an international term. However, it is used in different senses in various countries. For example, in England and the United States, all types of folk art are called poetry, music, dance, theater and applied arts, as well as myth, beliefs and traditions. In our Uzbek science, the term is becoming more specific. When I say “Folklore” the people are mainly understood oral information transmission. The terms “folklore”, “Uzbek folklore” were first introduced into Uzbek folklore by Zarif H. (1934-1935). Elements of folklore combine elements of music, dance, theater, so folklore is called syncretic art. At the same time, folklore works differ from other types of art.

In the most ancient literary monuments of many nations, such as myths and legends, in fairy tales there are similarities; this aspects is more heroism, which is the highest idea of man and his great, glorious mission on Earth. It is reflected in the hymns of gentleness, kindness and beauty. The only surviving example of the English Saxon epic, which originated among the Germanic tribes who immigrated to Britain, is The Song of Beowulf. The work was created in the VIII-IX centuries and was written in the early X century. The

epic is an ancient German typical of the pagan period myths, but in later times it also included Christian religious views. The epic has more than three thousand lines and consists of two parts [3: 12-13b].

Moreover, the similarities and commonalities between English and Uzbek folklore show that in the history of mankind the culture of all the nations began to develop equally. At the same time, it is a clear example of the complementarity and expansion of the folklore of the ideas is a clear confirmation of this idea.

The first writers, researchers and publishers of some examples of Uzbek folklore were European tourists, ambassadors and scientists who lived in the second half of the XIX century and the beginning of the XX century.

In Uzbek literature Luqmani Hakim is the image of a wise physician in Eastern classical literature and folk oral poetry. He is the hero of many stories, legends and fairy tales. Alisher Navoi (“ Historical ruler and prophet”), Khandamir (“ Ravzat us-safo”) and others portrayed Luqman as a ruling historical figure- prophet. In Eastern classical literature, he was a black slave who was freed by his prophetic prophecies. In Uzbek folklore, the image of a ruler Luqmani has become a symbol of wisdom.

On the other hand, English folk fairy tales are unique and diverse. Fabric heroes, impure forces, images of creatures, fairy tales, romance have a unique place in it. The heroes of some fairy tales are hardworking, wise, truthful, noble and brave, some of them have become real heroes of the people. For instance, in the fairy tale “Adventures of Jack and the Giant-Killer” Jack, the son of the farmer, is a cannibal. When he went into battle with the creatures he thought only of a reward, but then he became a real warrior in order to save his people from human abuse.

The heroes of other fairy tales are not among those who do this degree of good. They achieve their goals through deceit and deception. But in them originality is the main feature of entrepreneurial and courageous character. This feature was highly valued in the British because it was created at a time when capitalism was developing and bourgeois society was taking shape. “Molly Whoopie” Molly, in the fairy tale “Jack and the Beanstalk” Jack is happy for himself and his loved ones by deceiving cannibals.

In addition, the humor, which is unique to the British people, is also reflected in his stories. That is why most English fairy tales can be called humorous. There are similar versions of them in English folklore. For example, there are three versions of the tale of three bears. In the first variant, a golden curly-haired girl comes to the bear’s house, in the second a small old woman comes, and in the third a fox comes. The Gingerbread Man and

Johnny-cake are similar in many ways, but they are different. These tales are Russian in the structure. This fairy is similar to “Bogirsok”. Although “Catskin” and “Cap of Rushes” are similar in plot, it is important to learn the difference between them.

Every country has a special image of wisdom based on their history and culture. The studies show that there is a deep connection of this image among countries. Several poets, characters, and even creatures can be seen as a wise person by doing useful activities for the community. The images of such wise people in different areas of the folklore can be an educational example of how a person will be a hero in their culture. As an example, in English folklore the image of Beowulf appears as a brave, noble national hero who does not hesitate to sacrifice his life to help people and in Uzbek people have such a feeling for the image of Alpomish.

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